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The polar chart of Pedro Reinel (ca. 1521-1524): a diplomatic tool or a scientific argument?

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Abstract

A chart of the sixteenth century is extant in the Topkapi Palace Museum, in Istanbul, depicting the southern hemisphere in an azimuthal equidistant projection, and containing the earliest known representation of the southeast coast of South America, in the wake of Magellan and Elcano's circum-navigation. In this article, it is argued that astronomical observations of longitude were accommodated in the representation, and that the chart was produced in the specific context of the *Juntas* of Badajoz-Elvas, held between the representatives of the Spanish and Portuguese Crowns, to discuss the location and possession of the Spice Islands. It is shown that, while most of the geographic information depicted on the chart is of Portuguese origin, including Southeast Asia and the Moluccas, the southeast coast of South America was depicted using the information collected by Magellan's fleet while progressing to the south along the coast of Brazil. The absence of the Strait of Magellan constitutes clear evidence that the chart was produced using the information brought to Seville by the ship *San Antonio*, which had deserted the fleet in October 1520, before the passage to the Pacific Ocean was found. It is concluded that this chart is a unique historical monument in the history of cartography and history of science, at large: firstly, as the earliest material evidence of the effective use of astronomical methods to determine longitude in a nautical context; and secondly, as an expressive scientific argument used in a historical political negotiation.

Introduction

Among the few extant charts completed shortly after Magellan and Elcano's voyage of circumnavigation (1519-1522), the polar chart now kept at the Palace Museum of Topkapi, in Istanbul, is the most enigmatic.¹ Many disparate theories about its purpose, dating and place of construction have been proposed, since Marcel Destombes made the first study, in 1938. He was later followed by Albert Nunes, Destombes (1955), Cortesão & Mota (1960, 1987), and, more recently, by Dejanirah Couto (2013, 2019). Based on stylistic and calligraphic features, historians have unanimously attributed the work to either Pedro or his son Jorge Reinel.

Figure 1 – Anonymous polar chart of the southern hemisphere, 1521-1524 (courtesy of the Topkapi Palace Museum Manuscript Library, Hazine 1825).

Drawn on a square sheet of parchment and in bad state of conservation, the chart depicts the southern hemisphere in a polar azimuthal equidistant projection (Fig. 1). The presence of an unbounded margin with a large tear (which has removed part of inland Africa), where two cut

¹ The designation *chart*, instead of *map*, will be used throughout this text notwithstanding the fact that this is not strictly a nautical chart and was not intended for navigation. Despite of the use of a map projection foreign to marine navigation, the representation was copied from traditional charts and the cartographic conventions in the depiction of the coastlines and names are those of nautical cartography.

legends, OR[IENS] and [OCCID]ENS, can be seen, suggests that the original consisted of two hemispheres placed side by side, of which the northern one was ripped off. The chart represents the southern shores of Africa and South America, and the southern archipelagoes of Southeast Asia between Sumatra and a little east of Seram, comprising the Lesser Sunda and Banda islands, as well as the island of Bacan, placed exactly on the central meridian. Despite its poor condition and the presence of numerous stains caused by water and mold, most coastlines and place names are visible. Along the western side of South America is a long legend in red, reading: *hesta terra descubrio fernãdo de Magalhães* ("this land was discovered by Ferdinand Magellan"). However, only the eastern entrance to the Strait of Magellan is depicted, and no passage between the Atlantic and the Pacific Ocean can be seen (see Figure 3). This means, as explained below, that the representation of the region was based on information collected before Magellan's fleet reached the Pacific Ocean. Also noticeable is the presence of the Malvinas/Falkland Islands, rightly placed at about the same latitude as the entrance to the Strait, arguably the first known representation of the archipelago.

The charted area is enclosed by a circular Equator, graduated counterclockwise from 0° to 360° of longitude, sub-divided in one-degree intervals. The circular equidistant parallels are spaced at five degrees intervals of latitude, from 0° to 90° S, but are not graduated. On the top of the chart, the reference meridian (360°) cuts through the island of Seram and passes exactly over Bacan (*buxean*), the southernmost of the traditional five Spice Islands of the Moluccas. This is obviously the eastern Demarcation Line of the Treaty of Tordesillas, and its orientation along the vertical axis of the chart reveals its central relevance. Moreover, and considering that the remaining four islands of the Moluccas (all in the north hemisphere) lay a little to the west of Bacan, one can infer that the archipelago was likely represented in the Portuguese hemisphere. On the bottom, the Demarcation Line cuts through the north coast of Brazil a little to the west of the Amazon River's mouth, as in contemporaneous cartography.

The lack of *in situ* access to the manuscript and to images of adequate quality may explain the difficulties felt by the historians in interpreting the chart and drawing solid conclusions about the context of its production. I was recently authorized to examine the manuscript and take high resolution digital images of some parts. This has made possible to read most geographical names, see important details not easily discernible on a photograph and, finally, propose original conclusions about why, when and by whom the chart was produced. Because of the exceptional historical importance of this manuscript, the earliest known to depict the southern part of South America, a short review is made of some previous studies, before analyzing the chart in more detail and proposing my own conclusions.

No detailed description of the geographical content of the chart is made in this article, which is essentially focused on the context of its production and its connection with the dispute between the Portuguese and the Spanish Crowns over the location of the Spice Islands.

Previous literature

The first historian to call attention to this polar chart was Marcel Destombes, in a paper presented to the International Congress of Geography, held in Amsterdam, in 1938. Based on the information provided by Destombes, Albert Kammerer published a small article, in 1940, where the whole chart was first reproduced, later followed by a lengthier study posthumously added to his hefty work *La Mer Rouge* (Kammerer, 1952). In 1955, Destombes came back to the subject with a more detailed analysis, where a transcription of all the chart's geographical names is included. Armando Cortesão and Teixeira da Mota also made a study of the chart in their *Portugaliae Monumenta Cartographica* (1987, 39-41), first published in 1960 and then reprinted in 1987. More recently, Dejanirah Couto (2013; 2019a; 2019b) published three works focused on its presumed authors – the cartographers Pedro and Jorge Reinel – and the alleged role played by Antonio Pigafetta in bringing the chart to Istanbul. Finally, a chapter dedicated to the polar chart, with new material resulting from a recent *in-situ* examination of the manuscript, was included in Joaquim Alves Gaspar and Šima Krtalić's book "The Cartography of Magellan" (2023). Part of the present article, especially in what the literature review and the representation of Southeast Asia on the chart are concerned, is based on that text.

All previous authors, except for Cortesão and Mota, contended that the chart was started in Seville in 1519, by Pedro or Jorge Reinel, immediately before the departure of Magellan's fleet. Some (Destombes, Kammerer) further claimed that it was completed in 1522, following the arrival of the ship *Victoria* in Seville. The alternative interpretation of Cortesão and Mota is that the chart was drawn in Lisbon, probably by Pedro Reinel, after the *San Antonio*, the ship captained by Estêvão Gomes that had deserted Magellan's fleet before the Strait was crossed, arrived in Seville, in May 1521. This interpretation was based on two features of the chart: the fact that the Strait of Magellan is not depicted, thus refuting the hypothesis that the manuscript was finished upon the 1522 arrival of the *Victoria*; and the placement of the Moluccas to the west of the Demarcation Line, that is, within the Portuguese hemisphere.

A different interpretation was proposed by Couto (2019b), who suggested that the chart was taken aboard one of Magellan's ships, after being partially drawn by Pedro Reinel, and then completed during the voyage. Couto based her interpretation on three alleged features of the manuscript: the use of a different colour to draw the coastlines to the south of Rio de la Plata, from which she concluded that they were later added by a different hand; the presence of a complete Strait of Magellan, though barely discernible; and the placement of the Spice Islands within the Spanish hemisphere. In a further argument concerning the context in which the chart was discovered (that is, in a set of documents that may have belonged to Suleyman the Magnificent), Couto (2013, 2019a) took up an earlier thesis of Destombes that the manuscript was taken to Turkey (or to Rhodes, then ruled by the Ottomans) by Antonio Pigafetta.

I will now come back to some of these issues, making use of the material gathered in the recent examination of the manuscript, and taking into account contemporaneous textual sources not

hitherto considered. My study will be focused on the representations of South America and Southeast Asia, the ones directly related to Magellan and Elcano's circum-navigation.

Figure 2 – South America in the polar chart. Notice the red legend witnessing the arrival of Magellan's fleet to the region of the Strait, the presence of the Malvinas/Falkland Islands and the vertical Demarcation Line of the Treaty of Tordesillas.

The representation of South America

When Magellan's fleet arrived in South America, the coast to the south of Rio de la Plata was still uncharted and unexplored by Europeans. The last navigator sent to the region by the Crown of Castile was João Dias de Solis, in 1515, who sought to discover the passage from the Atlantic to the Pacific Ocean. But the navigator and some of his crew were killed by the natives while exploring Rio de la Plata, and the remaining two caravels of the fleet returned to Spain, where they arrived in 1516. Thus, cartography prior to Magellan's mission only depicts the coast down to Rio de la Plata. That is the case of the anonymous chart known as Kunstmann IV, completed shortly before the fleet left Seville, and of the chart of the Atlantic Ocean included in

the Miller Atlas, which was completed around the same date.² One of the main reasons for the historical relevance of this polar chart is, therefore, that it contains the earliest-known representation of the eastern coast of South America between Rio de la Plata and the entrance to the Strait of Magellan, including the Malvinas/Falklands islands. By the time it was produced, the existence of the Pacific Ocean had been known since 1513, when Spanish explorer Vasco Núñez de Balboa crossed the Isthmus of Panama and sighted the great *Mar del Sud* for the first time.

The two most striking features in the representation of South America on this chart (Fig. 3) are the red legend running along the western part of the continent (*hesta terra descubrio fernãdo de Magalhães*, “this land was discovered by Ferdinand Magellan”), witnessing the visit of Magellan’s fleet, and the depiction of the eastern entrance of what is now called the Strait of Magellan. It is clear from a close examination of the manuscript that no connection between the Atlantic and the Pacific Oceans is shown, as only a part of the Strait is represented, between the eastern entrance and what seems to be Dawson Island. This region was visited by the fleet in October 1520, before Estêvão Gomes deserted with the *San Antonio*.

Figure 3 – The southern tip of South America on the polar chart, with the eastern entrance of the Strait of Magellan and what seems the Dawson Island (East is up). No connection between the Atlantic and the Pacific Oceans is visible.

² The anonymous chart known as Kunstmann IV planisphere (ca. 1519), attributed to Jorge Reinell and Pedro Reinell, was lost during World War II. A black and white photo is extant, as well as a coloured fac-simile drawn in 1843 by Otto Progel, now kept at the Bibliothèque nationale de France (CPL GE AA-564 (RES)). The Miller Atlas (ca. 1519) is a luxurious manuscript containing ten charts and a map of the world, whose cover page is signed and dated by the Portuguese cartographer Lopo Homem. It is considered to have been also drawn by Pedro and Jorge Reinell and is now kept at the Bibliothèque nationale de France (Res. Ge. DD. 683). See Gaspar & Krtalić (2023), 127-135; 136-142.

The absence of a connection between the Atlantic and the Pacific Oceans on this chart indicates that it was drawn before the news of the crossing of the Strait arrived in Europe, that is, before the *Victoria* returned to Seville in 1522. The inevitable conclusion is that the necessary information may only have been brought by the deserting ship *San Antonio*, contradicting Couto's theory that the chart was taken aboard Magellan's ship (see also Fraile, 2017). This is reinforced by the fact that no differences are apparent in the colouring of the coastline to the south of Rio de la Plata, despite the claims of the same author, undermining the hypothesis that more than one hand was involved in the drafting of the chart.

Another intriguing feature of this chart, previously noted by Fraile (2017), is the presence of the Malvinas/Falklands, depicted as a single island. Because none of the extant written testimonies mention these islands, the most likely explanation is that they were sighted by the *San Antonio's* crew after leaving the Strait and turning away from the coast to take profit of the trade winds in the region.

In Fig. 4 (left) the eastern coast of South America depicted on the polar chart was reconstructed on a square graticule of meridians and parallels, so that it could be compared with the delineation on a modern map, which is represented by the red coastlines. The overlay was made by aligning the Demarcation Line of Tordesillas (in blue, coinciding with the chart's prime meridian) and all parallels in the two representations. A prominent feature, previously unnoticed by historians, is the placement of the entrance to the Strait of Magellan on its approximately correct longitude, relative to the Demarcation Line. That is not the case with the rest of the coastline, though, whose eastern displacement steadily increases from about three degrees, near the Strait, to about ten degrees, near 30° S.

It is a widely known fact that the east coast of Brazil appears shifted to the east in all Portuguese cartography of the early sixteenth century. The origin of this distortion was, most probably, the effect of magnetic declination on the compass directions collected by the pilots at sea, and later used to construct the charts. This is well illustrated by the Cantino planisphere (1502), as previously shown by Gaspar (2010, 161-163). Later on, however, this eastern displacement may have been maintained, if not exaggerated, with the purpose of including a larger part of Brazil in the Portuguese hemisphere. That is probably the case of the Kunstmann IV planisphere, and also the Atlantic chart of the Miller Atlas, where the coast to the north of Rio de la Plata appears displaced seven to nine degrees to the east. The same happens with this polar chart, thus confirming that the representation of most of the coast of Brazil was copied from Portuguese sources.

Figure 4 – On the left, a reconstruction of the east coast of South America in the polar chart on a square graticule of meridians and parallels (black line), compared with a modern map (the Demarcation Line of Tordesillas is the blue meridian); on the right, the same outline was overlaid on the Castiglione planisphere (1525). The overlays were made aligning the Demarcation Line and the latitudes on all representations.

The same coastal outline was overlaid on the anonymous Castiglione planisphere of 1525, attributed to Diogo Ribeiro (Fig. 4, right), which is considered to have been copied from the Spanish *Padrón Real*, that is, the official master chart.³ Notice the agreement between the orientation of the coast between the Strait and Rio de la Plata in both representations. The strange bulge of the polar chart, pushing the coast between Rio de la Plata and Rio de Janeiro more than five degrees to the east, when compared with the Castiglione planisphere, constitutes a marked divergence. This will be analyzed later, in the present section.

Coming back to the depiction of the Strait on the chart, whose longitude is close to the correct value, the possibility that its position was manipulated by either the Portuguese (who produced the chart) or the Spanish (who navigated along the coast) should be ruled out. Indeed, displacing the coastal stretch south of Rio de la Plata to the east would benefit neither of them, because the Demarcation Line on available cartography (produced by the Portuguese) ran

³ The anonymous chart known as Castiglione planisphere was completed in 1525, in the Casa de la Contratación of Seville, to be offered to Count Baldassare Castiglione, apostolic nuncio to Pope Clement VII in Madrid, on the occasion of the marriage of Emperor Charles V (Carlos I of Spain) with Princess Isabel of Portugal. It is now kept in the Biblioteca Estense Universitaria, Modena (C.G.A.12). See Cortesão & Mota, Vol. I (1987), 95-97; Martín-Merás (1993), 91-99; Martínez (1994), 183-192 and Gaspar & Krtalić (2023), 168-172.

precisely through the northern margin of Rio de la Plata's mouth. The only way to put significantly more territory inside one hemisphere or the other would be to shift the whole coastline to the east, adding to the existing distortion and further benefiting the Portuguese, or to the west, thus reducing the distortion and benefiting the Spanish. Two possible sources of data could have been used to represent this coastal stretch: the navigational information collected by the fleet, while sailing southward from Rio de la Plata; or the longitude determined astronomically by the chief pilot-cosmographer Andrés de San Martín in San Julián, on April 17, 1520.

To evaluate the first option, we need to calculate the direction of the rhumb line connecting Rio de la Plata (where the fleet made a stopover in January 1520) to the entrance of the Strait: 209°, counting clockwise from North. This line would put the entrance of the Strait more than seven degrees to the east of its actual position on the chart. If we further consider the effect of magnetic declination in 1520 (about 5° East in the region), which was not corrected at the time, the new direction (204°) would further move the end point of the path more than two degrees to the east.⁴ Comparing this course with the direction measured on the chart between Rio de la Plata and the Strait (222°) we arrive at a mistake of 18 degrees, an error too large to be reasonably ascribed to either the cartographer or the pilots.⁵

Having excluded the hypothesis that the orientation of the coast between Rio de la Plata and the Strait was based on traditional navigational information, we are left with the possibility that longitude measurements were used to depict the area close to the Strait. We know, from the testimony of the chroniclers João de Barros Fernão Lopes de Castanheda, who had access to his notes in Lisbon (Barros, 1628; Castanheda, 1554) that astronomical observations were made by the chief cosmographer-pilot Andrés de San Martín, on the east coast of South America: on the 17th of December, 1519, in Rio de Janeiro (conjunction of the Moon and Jupiter); on the 1st of February of 1520 (opposition between Moon and Venus); on the 23rd of February of 1520

⁴ An explanation is needed about why that course of 209° does not coincide with the one measured on the modern map. The reason is that loxodromic directions are not conserved on a cylindrical equidistant projection (the projection of the modern map), a property only observed on the Mercator projection. But nautical charts of the time, where the parallels were equally spaced, were not constructed using any explicit map projection. Directions measured with the marine compass were transferred directly to the chart, not correcting for magnetic declination, and ignoring that they had been measured on the spherical surface of the Earth. The result led to geometric inconsistencies, in the sense that only the specific tracks used to construct the charts were correctly represented. *All other directions* measured on them were affected by variable errors. This fact was first noticed by the mathematician Pedro Nunes in his *Tratado en defensam da carta de marear* of 1537 ("Treatise in defense of the navigational chart"), where he drew attention to the fact that most directions, including the north-south direction, were incorrectly depicted on the contemporaneous charts. The significant detail to note in this specific situation is that the coast of Brazil on sixteenth century's cartography would be correctly oriented, for navigational purposes, if it were represented on the charts in accordance with the *compass courses* made by the ships along the shoreline. The effect of a spatially variable magnetic declination on the orientation of the coastlines would not be noticed by the mariners because navigation when also made with the same type of magnetic compasses. A more detailed explanation of these subject is in Gaspar (2007; 2010, 66-73).

⁵ The fact that the fleet did not navigate on a straight line between Rio de la Plata is irrelevant here. Using a composite track more representative of the real route along the coast would produce a similar result.

(Moon and Sun); and on 17th of April of 1520, in San Julián (total eclipse of the Sun). We also know, from the same sources, that the result of the observations made in Rio de Janeiro was rejected because of its very large error, and that San Julián was found to be 61° west of Seville, to which corresponds a longitude error of only 0.6°. ⁶

The fact that a total eclipse of the Sun occurred on April 17, 1520, about two weeks after the fleet arrived in the bay of San Julián to winter, cannot be a coincidence. Given that measuring longitudes along the way was a critical requirement of the mission, San Martín must have carefully consulted the available astronomical ephemerides and identified the adequate time to make the observations. We know that he took with him two astronomical almanacs, based on the original tables of Abraham Zacut (1498; 1502): one taking Salamanca as the reference place, and the other using Toledo. From the analysis of those tables, we know that the local time of the phenomenon at the reference meridian was affected by about 27 minutes for the Toledo tables (to which corresponds a longitude error of about 7° E), and 86 minutes for the Salamanca tables (to which corresponds a longitude error of about 21.5°). No corrections were considered by San Martín for the error caused by parallax. Although the cosmographer was certainly aware of its considerable effect, no adequate correction tables were available to him for the latitude of the observations. According to Romeu Gaspar (2023), the error caused by the uncorrected parallax almost exactly compensated for the one affecting the local time of the phenomenon in the Salamanca tables, thus explaining the very accurate longitude value obtained by San Martín.⁷ The fortuitous quality of this value does not diminish the care and mastery revealed by the cosmographer in the series of observations carried out along the coast of South America, as revealed by the testimony of the chroniclers, neither does it put in question its pioneering nature.

Having arrived at the conclusion that the position of the Strait on the polar chart was based on a longitude measurement made by Andrés de San Martín, we still need to explain why the coast between Rio de la Plata and Rio de Janeiro was pushed further to the east, contradicting

⁶ For the list of astronomical observations of San Martín, see João de Barros (1628, Capitulo X, fl. 147). For the value of longitude determined by San Martín (61° measured from Seville), see Fernão Lopes de Castanheda (1924, 159-160). The principle underlying the determination of the longitude at the time, which had been known since the Antiquity, consisted in comparing the local times of the occurrence of certain astronomical phenomena (like an eclipse) in two different places. Knowing the longitude of one of them, the difference between the two local times would immediately give the longitude of the other, considering that the celestial sphere apparently rotates 15 degrees per hour (or 1 degree in 4 minutes). Because of the inconvenience of having two observers in different places, whose measurements could only be compared *a posteriori*, astronomical ephemerides were available giving the local times of astronomical phenomena in reference places, like conjunctions and oppositions of heavenly bodies. For an estimation of the errors associated with the astronomical determination of longitudes during the sixteenth century, see Gaposchkin and Haramundanis (2007); Steele and Stephenson (1998).

⁷ A lengthier explanation of the various errors affecting the observation is provided by Romeu Gaspar (2023). This author suggests that San Martín purposely discarded the Toledo tables, either because he detected a typographic error in the position of the Moon (which explains the different local times of the phenomenon), or because the longitude of San Julián determined with them would be inconsistent with the navigational data collected along the east coast of South America.

Portuguese cartography of the time. As Rolando Laguarda Trías (1975, 160) justly noted, the observation of the opposition between the Moon and Venus on the 1st of February of 1520, mentioned by Barros, could only have occurred when the fleet was leaving the Rio de la Plata estuary, according to the log of Francesco Albo (2018, 72). In fact, a near opposition of the two heavenly bodies occurred near 6 AM, when the Moon was setting below the horizon and Venus was rising. It could well be that this occurrence was used by San Martín to determine longitude, and that the coastline to the north of Rio de la Plata was adjusted accordingly. This correction would be ultimately rejected in the official Spanish cartography, or maybe by San Martín himself.

The fact that the longitudinal position of the Strait and the orientation of the eastern coast of South America approximately coincide with the ones in the Spanish official cartography that followed (except for the bulge north of Rio de la Plata) demonstrates that Estêvão Gomes, the captain of the *San Antonio*, had access to crucial navigational information before returning to Spain: not necessarily to San Martín's data but, more likely, to cartographic sketches that might have been produced along the way. In fact, this second possibility may explain why the coast at the latitude of San Julián, as depicted on the chart, is slightly displaced to the east (about three degrees) in relation to the longitude value determined by San Martín.

How this information reached the author of the polar chart is a different matter. Assuming that it was indeed made by one of the Reinel, as unanimously accepted by historians, the easiest explanation is that the cartographer was still in Seville when the *San Antonio* returned. An alternative possibility is that information was passed to him by some informer who had access to the data brought by the ship.

The representation of Southeast Asia

Because the surviving part of the polar chart only depicts the southern hemisphere, most regions visited by the fleet of Magellan and Elcano, during its southward progression from the Philippines to Timor (between March 1521 and January 1522) are not shown. This includes four of the five traditional Moluccas, as well as the large island of Halmahera, both situated north of the Equator. Fig. 5 shows the representation of the region from Sumatra (*camatra*), in the west, to an unidentified island (*y. dos homēs brancos*, 'island of the white men') in the east, together with an outline of the coasts containing the transcription of the place names. The representation includes Java, the Lesser Sunda, Timor, and the complex set of islands of the Banda archipelago. The larger island near the northeast corner is Seram, and the blue island to the north of the Lesser Sunda (*çelebes*) is a misrepresented Sulawesi.⁸ The small island placed exactly on the line of demarcation, just below the Equator, is Bacan (*buxean*), the southernmost of the five Spice Islands. Knowing that the remaining four Moluccas lay to the north and a little to the west of Bacan (thus, in the Portuguese hemisphere), the possibility of this millimetric

⁸ For a more detailed description of the depiction of Southeast Asia on this chart, see Gaspar & Krtalić (2023).

Knowing that the remaining four islands are located to the north, almost perfectly aligned on a north-south line that runs a little to the west of Bacan (Fig. 6, right), we may assume that the chart must have placed them within the Portuguese hemisphere. Although this conjecture cannot be directly confirmed, in the absence of the northern half of the chart, a related piece of information lends it additional plausibility. This evidence is found in a letter sent to the Portuguese king João III in May 1524, from his representatives to the *Juntas* of Badajoz-Elvas, where the location and possession of the Moluccas were being discussed with the representatives of the king of Spain.⁹ The main subject of the letter is the prospect of switching the hitherto tacit origin of the 370 leagues mentioned in the Treaty of Tordesillas (that is, the westmost island of Santo Antão) to a more central position within the Cape Vert archipelago. Such an adjustment would also displace the position of the eastern Demarcation Line, putting the Moluccas well inside the Portuguese hemisphere on the contemporary cartography.¹⁰ It is within the scope of the discussion that this letter makes an intriguing reference to a chart that was brought to the meeting:

Ca temos hua carta que Pero Afonso trouxe de Lixboa doutro padrão de Pero Reinei que midindo de Sant'Amtam nos da por mui pouco Maluquo. Polla qual carta nunca navegarão que se fez pera el rei que santa gloria aja e assi a de Diogo Ribeiro e a de Bernaldo Pirez fazem por nos de qualquer parte que meção e nom temos nem a i em Purtugal mais cartas que por nos fação. E se lhe pidimos licença pera mostrar cartas e pomas foi porque sabemos que nos ao demostrar muitas em seu favor pera se ver a diversidade das cartas e virmos a medida do ceo e eclipses porque nos em contrayro das suas lhes mostraremos estas que fazem em nosso favor ainda que ho que destes homens podemos entender seu fundamento he midir toda a terra polla extimativa que he cartas com que se navegua a India.

Here we have a chart that Pedro Afonso brought from Lisbon [made] from another pattern of Pedro Reinel which, measuring from Santo Antão, barely gives us the Moluccas. By that chart they never sailed, [and] it was made for the king *que santa gloria aja* [who may reach glory, that is, who had recently passed away], and so, the one [chart] of Diogo Ribeiro and of Bernaldo Pirez do for us [are in our favour] from whatever part they measure, and we don't have, not even in Portugal, more charts that do for us. And if we asked your permission to show charts and globes it was because, when showing many [charts] in your favour in order to see the diversity of the charts and see the measurement of the sky and eclipses because we, contrary to theirs, will show to them these [charts] which are in our favour, although what we can understand from these men is that their grounding is to measure all land from the estimate of the charts used to navigate to India.

⁹ This letter was sent from Badajoz, on May 18, 1524, by three representatives of king João II of Portugal: Francisco de Mello, Pedro Afonso de Aguiar and Diogo Lopez. See 'Carta dos deputados que tinham sido enviados para tratar do negócio de Maluco'. Badajoz, 18 Maio 1524, in *As Gavetas da Torre do Tombo*, IV (Gav. XV, Maços 1-15). Lisboa, Centro de Estudos Históricos Ultramarinos, 1964, 341-348.

¹⁰ According to the terms of the Treaty of Tordesillas, the Line of Demarcation between the two Iberian hemispheres should pass 370 leagues (a little more than 2 000 km) to the west of the Cape Vert islands. Although no explicit agreement was reached on this matter, the tacit interpretation was that the westmost island of the archipelago should be taken as origin of the counting.

That is, a chart made from a pattern of Pedro Reinel for king Manuel I (who died in December 1521) had been brought to the *Juntas*, in which the distance from Santo Antão to the Moluccas barely put the archipelago inside the Portuguese hemisphere. All these elements (authorship, date of production, and the non-navigational purpose of the chart) match the polar chart too perfectly to be a coincidence. Other features, such as the presence of the Demarcation Line matching the vertical axis of the chart and the choice of a polar azimuthal projection, further suggest that the chart was made to facilitate the visualization of the Earth under the terms of the Treaty of Tordesillas. By accepting that the chart mentioned in this letter is indeed our polar chart, we may also infer that the four northern Moluccas were there placed at a very small distance to the west of the Demarcation Line (that is, hardly within the Portuguese hemisphere).

The mere suggestion of displacing the origin of the Tordesillas agreement to the east of Santo Antão, a change that would never be accepted by the Spanish Crown, reveals a fundamental weakness in the Portuguese diplomatic position. The same weakness can be perceived in the realization that there were very few Portuguese charts where the Moluccas were conveniently placed, and in the wish to show as many as possible of those charts.¹¹ An important detail of the letter is the mention of astronomical observations made by the Portuguese, apparently used (the text is not entirely clear) to make some charts. In this respect, however, its authors expressed their incredulity that such an argument would ever be considered by the Spanish representatives, because of their insistence in only relying on the traditional charts used to sail to India.

A complex issue that still needs to be clarified is the criteria used by the cartographer to plot the Moluccas on the polar chart. Given the millimetric placement of Bacan, exactly on the Demarcation Line, we may be driven to hastily conclude that this was an *ad hoc* expedient motivated by diplomatic convenience.¹² But there are two other possibilities. The first is that the longitude recorded by the pilot Francesco Albo in the Philippines, which is considered to have been based on measurements made by San Martín (see, for example, Laguardia Trías, 1975), was known by the Portuguese before the chart was completed. The second is that the Moluccas were depicted according to longitude measurements made by the Portuguese, as seems to be implied by the text of the letter.

I will begin by evaluating the first hypothesis. The longitude measurement made in the Philippines could have been known by the Portuguese on three different occasions: while the fleet was still in the region; after the return of the *Victoria* to Seville, in September 1522; and

¹¹ Before Magellan's mission, all extant charts of Portuguese origin depicted the Moluccas in the Spanish hemisphere. That is the case of the anonymous chart of the Indian Ocean (ca. 1517), attributed to Pedro Reinel, and of the Kunstmann IV planisphere, made by Jorge and Pedro Reinel ca. 1519, to be offered to the king Carlos I of Spain. See Gaspar & Krtalić (2023).

¹² In fact, the correct longitudinal position of Bacan relative to the antimeridian is about five degrees further to the west, that is, well within the Portuguese hemisphere.

when the documents from the Trinidad, apprehended by the Portuguese in the Moluccas, arrived in Lisbon. The first hypothesis is to be ruled out, because there was no contact between the Spanish ships and the Portuguese before the Victoria left the region. The second possibility is unlikely for a more subtle reason. Although Francesco Albo was received by the king upon the arrival of the Victoria, he immediately disappeared from the scene and there is no evidence that his log ever fell into the hands of the Portuguese. Of course, the Spanish Crown was perfectly aware of the longitude measurements made by Andrés de San Martín in Southeast Asia. Whether or not they trusted them, such embarrassing evidence could represent a serious setback for the Spanish diplomatic position. The very reason that an experienced observer was sent on the mission was that the Crown wished to add irrefutable scientific proof to its inner conviction that the islands lay within the Spanish hemisphere. Thus, it is no surprise that all contrary evidence was wiped off, and the Spanish subsequently refused to make further astronomical longitude measurements to settle the dispute. It is consequently quite unlikely that the Spice Islands on the polar chart were depicted according to longitude information brought aboard the Victoria. We may then turn to the third possibility, that the Moluccas on the chart was copied from the documentation apprehended from the Trinidad. This hypothesis should also be ruled out, for two reasons: firstly, because those documents only arrived in Lisbon in 1526, after the chart was completed and the *Juntas* were over; and secondly, because they did not contain any information about the measurements made by San Martín in Southeast Asia. Had they included those data, the Portuguese chroniclers who had access to the documents would have mentioned them. It is wholly reasonable that, immediately before returning to Europe with the Victoria, Sebastian Elcano has taken from the damaged flagship Trinidad critical data pertaining to the longitude measurements made in the region.

We are thus left with the last explanation: that the Moluccas were represented on the polar chart using longitude measurements made by the Portuguese. Assuming, from the reasons explained above, that the chart was copied from a pattern produced for the Portuguese king Manuel I (who died in December 1521) by Pedro Reinel, those measurements must have been made some time before. In a note written around 1524 (probably addressed to the Portuguese Crown), someone (who signed L.P.) writing in the name the Duke of Bragança claimed that nautical charts should not be used to demarcate the Portuguese and Spanish hemispheres, due to the many falsities afflicting them. He proposed instead the use of eclipses to determine longitudes, and offered two examples of observations made by the Portuguese in the Indian Ocean, aimed at correcting its exaggerated width on charts.¹³

¹³ That these longitude measurements were related to the on-going discussion about the position of the Spice Islands, which were situated within the Spanish hemisphere on contemporary Portuguese cartography, seems obvious. The cause for the mistake is here implicitly attributed to an exaggeration of the Indian Ocean width, caused by the incompetence of pilots. However, both claims were wrong: the width of the Indian Ocean was, in fact, slightly underestimated on the charts; and the real cause for the displacement of all lands to the east of Africa was its eastward displacement and stretching, caused by the effect of magnetic declination on the compass

Se demonstra mais craramente a falsydade das cartas polas experientias de alguuns eclipsis que são tomados a saber huum que tomou Bernaldo Pirez peramte muitas testemunhas vinte ou trinta e cinco legoas aaquem de Malaqua e outro que tomou Diego Lopez de Sequeira antre a India e Arabia hamde se mostra aveer falsydade de Malaqua a este pomto deste eclipsi que tomou Diego Lopez de Sequeira mais de setecentas legoas [...]

One can demonstrate more clearly the falseness of the charts with the experiments of some eclipses which were taken, namely the one by Bernarldo Pirez in front of many witnesses, twenty or thirty-five leagues short of Malacca, and another by Diego Lopez de Sequeira between India and Arabia, where it is shown the falsity [in the distance] from Malacca to this point where the eclipse was taken by Diego Lopez de Sequeira by more than seven hundred leagues [...]

Exactly when those astronomical measurements were made is unknown, but the possibilities are not many. We know that a total eclipse of the Moon occurred on the 6th of November of 1519, and also a total eclipse of the sun on the 7th of April of 1521, both visible in the Indian Ocean and Malacca. A possible interpretation of the text is that the same phenomenon was observed by both Pirez and Sequeira. If that were the case, the errors in the astronomical tables used by them (assuming they were the same) would be cancelled in the determination of the longitude difference between the two places. But such a possibility seems to be denied by the exaggeration of more than 700 leagues (40 degrees of longitude) alleged in the letter. In fact, contemporaneous Portuguese cartography placed Malacca at about 48 degrees (840 leagues) east of Cape Guardafui (at the entrance of the Gulf of Aden), which represents an underestimation of about three degrees. Assuming that this was not an unintended mistake, not only the possibility of simultaneous observations should be rejected but also one or both observations were affected by serious blunders. This would also imply that the author of the letter (probably a secretary of the duke) was unaware of the real dimensions of the Indian Ocean and how it was depicted on contemporaneous cartography.

Thus, although it seems undeniable that longitude measurements were made in the Indian Ocean to correct the position of the Moluccas on Portuguese cartography, no reliable information is extant concerning their outcome. A reasonable conservative conclusion is that, although the results of those observation may have been considered (as suggested in the letter sent by the Portuguese representatives at the *Juntas*, above), the final placement of the archipelago on the polar chart was artificially adjusted.¹⁴

directions used to construct the charts. This fact was only fully explained by João de Castro in 1538, in his *Roteiro de Lisboa a Goa* (Rutter from Lisbon to Goa).

¹⁴ Although the observation of eclipses was universally acknowledged as the best method to determine longitude, the astronomers of the time were aware of the fact that only repeated observations taken over a long period could guarantee accurate results. The earliest extant Portuguese charts depicting the region after 1524 are those

Conclusions

In this article, the content and historical context surrounding the production of the sixteenth century Portuguese polar chart kept in Istanbul were addressed. The results of the investigation indicate that the manuscript was copied from a pattern chart made by the cartographer Pedro Reinel for the Portuguese king Manuel I, between May 1521 (when the deserting ship *San Antonio* arrived in Seville) and December 1521 (when the king died). The chart accommodates two sets of geographical information with different origins: one collected by Magellan's fleet when sailing along the southeast coast of South America, between December 1519 and October 1520; and the other gathered in Southeast Asia by the Portuguese from 1511 onwards. It was further concluded that this chart was used in the specific context of the *Juntas* of Badajoz-Elvas, held in April-May 1524, when the representatives of the two Iberian Crowns discussed the location and possession of the Moluccas. We may thus conclude that the manuscript was concluded between 1521 (when Pedro Reinel's model was drafted) and 1524, when it was brought to the *Juntas*.¹⁵ To the question proposed in the title of the article, of whether the polar chart was made as a diplomatic instrument or a scientific argument, I find both to have been within the aims of the cartographer.

In some respects, this chart constitutes a milestone in the history of cartography, as well as in the history of science at large. Firstly, it is the earliest known material evidence of the effective use of astronomical determinations of longitude on a representation of the Earth produced in a navigational context. Although the astronomical tables of the time (especially for the position of the moon and planets) were far from perfect, and the quality of results greatly depended on the skill of the observers, it was shown how at least one longitude determined astronomically was incorporated into the polar chart. Secondly, this chart is an example of how a scientific stance – the proposed use of measured longitudes to solve a diplomatic dispute between the Portuguese and the Spanish – could be eloquently presented in cartographic form. By replacing the usual projectionless nautical chart with a map drawn in a mathematical projection, where parallels and meridians were sharply delineated and the Demarcation Line appeared aligned with its vertical axis, the Portuguese were making an appeal to authority: the learned ranks of cosmographers and astronomers over the artisanal know-how of pilots and chart makers. It is somehow ironic that this powerful argument was supported by the observations made by a Spanish pilot and cosmographer – Andrés de San Martín – on a Spanish mission.

contained in the anonymous atlas of ca. 1537 attributed to Gaspar Viegas, where the Moluccas are depicted with a longitudinal error of less than one degree. By that time, the Portuguese have already had the opportunity to make several astronomical determinations of longitude in the region. For a list of the position of the Moluccas on European charts of the sixteenth century, see Gaspar & Krtalić (2023).

¹⁵ How the manuscript was later found in possession of the Ottoman Turks is more difficult to explain. It might well be that it was taken from Lisbon to Spain, together with other documentation that included the notes of Andrés de San Martín, during the Iberian Union (1580-1640). The large European territory then ruled by the Spanish monarchs may make it easier to explain how it ended up in Turkish hands.

Ultimately, the Spanish resisted the use of measured longitudes to resolve the issue – arguing that the proposal of making astronomical observations in the region was a dilatory manoeuvre – and continued to take refuge in the distorted contemporaneous cartography. In the end, the political power of Emperor Charles V prevailed over any scientific arguments, forcing the Crown of Portugal to pay a large amount of money to keep its commercial monopoly in Southeast Asia. One of the likely reasons for this outcome was that the Portuguese were not absolutely sure about the location of the Moluccas, and could not produce convincing evidence in favour of their position. If more robust astronomical measurements were available, they would certainly have been used in the negotiations.

We could finally ask if, after Magellan and Elcano's mission, longitudes determined by astronomical methods started to be used in navigation and nautical cartography. The answer to this question is an emphatic no. In fact, this unique achievement of determining longitudes during a maritime voyage and reflecting them on a map had little to do with navigation and nautical cartography, and all to do with politics. More than two centuries would pass until longitudes started to be routinely determined on board, and charts were constructed using geographical coordinates. One of the reasons for this delay was the lack of *accurate* ephemerides tables containing the positions of the heavenly bodies in the sky, from which the longitude of the observer could be determined *at any time*, and not only at the rare instances when a conjunction or opposition occurred. When Andrés de San Martín made his observations, those tables did not exist, and the typical accuracy of the longitude measurements was not good enough for navigational purposes. Adequate astronomical methods only became available well into the eighteenth century, with the publication of accurate tables containing the position of the Moon at any time, permitting the method of lunar distances to be used effectively on board. This development was synchronous with the introduction of the maritime chronometer, which much simplified the determination of longitude, marking a turning point in the history of navigation and nautical cartography.

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